

INFLUENCE OF MULTIVITAMIN PRODUCT HI BEES ON BROOD REARING AND ON TOTAL PROTEIN IN HEMOLYMPH OF HONEYBEES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we assessed the influence of multivitamin product HI BEES (vitamins B2, B5, B12, C and E) on brood rearing and on total protein in hemolymph of adult bees. Honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) colonies were divided into 2 groups, each of 7 colonies: control group fed with 350 ml of sugar syrup twice a week and experimental group fed with 350 ml sugar syrup supplemented with HI BEES vitamins. We measured sealed worker brood cells in 12 days intervals during spring and autumn feeding. Composite samples of bees from experimental and control groups for total protein measurement were taken three times and levels of total protein were determined spectrophotometrically. The experiments were carried out from April to October 2024. Bee colonies treated with HI BEES vitamins had higher numbers of brood cells and higher levels of total protein in hemolymph than control colonies.

Key words: Honey bee, brood rearing, total protein, vitamins, HI BEES.

Introduction

It is well known that adding multivitamins and multimineral to the sugar syrup has positive effect on the development of honeybee colonies (Anđelković *et al.* 2011). Providing honeybees with amino acids and multivitamins protects bees from immunosuppression induced by microsporidian *Nosema ceranae* (Fries *et al.* 1996) and helps to reduce *Nosema* spore counts (Glavinic *et al.* 2017). Honeybee colonies need vitamins B complex for brood rearing; 5.4 µg of vitamin B6 is necessary to rear one larva to the capped stage (Anderson et Dietz 1976). Colonies given vitamin B complex showed increase in colony strength and had lower counts of *Nosema ceranae* spores as well as lower acute bee paralysis virus, deformed wing virus and sacbrood virus loads (Jovanovic *et al.* 2021). Colonies received vitamin C had increased brood areas; vitamin C also had positive effect on hypopharyngeal glands development (Zahra et Talal 2008). Feeding vitamin C not only leads to brood increase in colonies, but has a positive effect on protein content in the bodies of worker bees (Andi et Ahmadi 2014). Similarly, product IMMUNOSTART HERB (vitamin C, flavonoids, polyphenols, polysaccharides, amino acids, essential oils, minerals) influences positively brood cells, hypopharyngeal glands development and levels of total protein in hemolymph (Shumkova et Balkanska 2021). Feeding colonies with vitamin C also improves activity of honeybees' antioxidative enzymes, increases protein content of emerging adult bees and helps to reduce winter colony losses by 33% (Farjan *et al.* 2012). In addition to improved antioxidant status and increased protein content of emerging adults, colonies fed with vitamin C also had lower infestations with *Varroa destructor* (Farjan *et al.* 2014). Since adding salts of microelement Co influences positively colony productivity and metabolism of vitamin C in honeybees, it is not surprising that Zhelyazkova *et al.* (2008) found increased brood cells and yields after application of product Startovit (Co, P,

sodium and chlorine ions) to honeybee colonies. To date, there are few studies about influence of fat-soluble vitamins to honeybees. Colonies added with vitamins A, D, E and K in the diet rear more brood; colonies fed vitamin A or vitamin K have shown the same results (Herbert et Shimanuki 1978). Product Apitonus (vitamin E, carbohydrates, methionine) increases brood cells in colonies during spring (Zhelyazkova *et al.* 2008).

As seen, positive effects of vitamins on brood rearing and productivity parameters of honeybee colonies generally have been proven. However, only few researchers (Farjan *et al.* 2012, 2014; Andi et Ahmadi 2014; Shumkova et Balkanska 2021) studied the link between vitamins supplementation and protein content or total protein in hemolymph in worker bees.

Here, we assessed the influence of multivitamin product HI BEES (vit. B2, B5, B12, C and E) on brood rearing and on levels of total protein in bee hemolymph.

Materials and Methods

Honey bee (*Apis mellifera*) colonies were kept in Langstroth hives at apiary of Institute of Animal Science – Kostinbrod, Bulgaria, according to standard beekeeping practices. All colonies were given one-year-old sister queens. Before the experiment, all colonies were equalized by equalising the quantity of bees, amount of honey and amount of pollen supply. The colonies were divided into 2 groups: control group fed with 350 ml sugar syrup and experimental group fed with 350 ml sugar syrup supplemented with HI BEES (Serdika Pharma Ring, Bulgaria) product (vit. B2, B5, B12, C and E) according to manufacturer's instructions. Each group consisted of 7 colonies and was fed twice a week. Number of brood cells was measured in 12 days intervals by using wired frame with 5/5 cm squares. The number of cells in one square is equal to 100 (Delaplane *et al.* 2013). For evaluation of total protein in hemolymph samples of 200 bees from each experimental and control colony were taken. The hemolymph was collected by puncturing the bee heart with microcapillary tubes at the level of 3rd dorsal tergite and composite samples of hemolymph for each colony were created. Before the analysis hemolymph samples were stored at -20 °C. Total protein concentration in hemolymph was determined spectrophotometrically with UV-Vis spectrophotometer (PG Instruments) at 530 nm (Kingsley 1939).

All trials were carried from April to October 2024. A total of 6 brood measurements were made during spring feeding of bee colonies (April – June) and 4 brood measurements during autumn feeding (September – October). Samples of bees for total protein measurement were taken three times (May, June and October).

Honeybees are not subjects of ethical regulations, therefore confirmation for relevant regulatory standards from Institute's Ethics Committee was not needed.

After testing the data for normality, Student t-tests were used to determine the significance of the differences between experimental and control groups in sealed brood cells and total protein in hemolymph. The statistical unit was bee colony resp. composite hemolymph sample from the colony. Level of statistical significance of all tests was defined as $\alpha = 0.05$. All analyses were performed with SPSS statistical software, version 23.0.

Results

Honeybee colonies were taking well sugar syrup containing multivitamin product HI BEES; no adverse effects were observed after application. The results from brood measurements for spring period are shown on Fig. 1A.

Figure 1: (A) Numbers of sealed brood cells of experimental and control groups during spring 2024. The sample size (n) was 7 colonies for experimental and 7 colonies for control group. (B) Box plot diagram with minimal, maximal and median values of numbers of sealed brood cells for spring 2024.

As seen, honeybee colonies which received HI BEES vitamins showed higher numbers of brood cells than control colonies on all dates except the first one. Brood differences between experimental and control groups were highly significant overall ($p < 0.001$) and statistically significant on all dates after 19.04.2024 (all $p < 0.001$). Box plot diagram of spring feeding is shown on Fig. 1B. During the autumn feeding (Fig. 2A) the tendency of better development of experimental colonies than control colonies persisted.

Figure 2: (A) Numbers of sealed brood cells of experimental and control groups during autumn 2024. The sample size (n) was 7 colonies for experimental and 7 colonies for control group. (B) Box plot diagram with minimal, maximal and median values of numbers of sealed brood cells for autumn 2024.

The differences in numbers of brood cells between the two groups were highly significant both overall ($p < 0.001$) and on all dates (all $p < 0.001$). The marked differences between experimental

and control group can also be seen on the box plot diagram for autumn feeding (Fig. 2B). Analysis of hemolymph samples revealed significant differences on total protein concentration between experimental and control colonies in all three measurements (all $p < 0.001$, Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Levels of total protein in hemolymph of experimental and control colonies during spring-autumn 2024. The sample size (n) was 7 hemolymph samples for experimental and 7 hemolymph samples for control group. With asterisks are marked groups which had significant differences to the other group at the respective time points.

The differences in total protein between the two groups were also highly significant overall ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Our results show that HI BEES vitamins stimulate brood rearing of honeybee colonies both in spring and autumn feeding. These findings are in agreement with Jovanovic *et al.* (2021) who found significant increase in colony strength after application of vitamin B complex. Because HI BEES product also contains vitamin C our findings corroborate the results of Zahra et Talal (2008) who reported increased numbers of brood cells in colonies after vitamin C application. Further, our results support the findings of Andi et Ahmadi (2014) who showed that supplementation of bee colonies with vitamin C during spring increases brood cells, colony population, body weight and protein content of worker bees. The findings of positive effect of product IMMUNOSTART HERB (which contain vit. C) on brood cells (Shumkova et Balkanska 2021) are also similar to the results of the current study. In conclusion, our current findings about the influence of HI BEES vitamins on bee colonies successfully establish a strong foundation to justify larger-scale experiments in the future.

It is common knowledge that hemolymph contains proteins essential for immunity, nutrient transport, and stress response (Feng *et al.* 2014). Significant positive correlations were found between proteins in hemolymph and colony performance parameters while *Varroa* infestation was negatively correlated with hemolymph proteins (Rudelli *et al.* 2024). An increase of protein curcumin in hemolymph also has been shown to have a positive effect on the lifespan of bees, on their

immunity and on resistance to pathogens such as *Nosema* spp. (Strachecka *et al.* 2015). Supplementing colonies with amino acids and multivitamins was found to protect bees from immunosuppression induced by *Nosema ceranae* (Fries *et al.* 1996) and to reduce spore counts (Glavinic *et al.* 2017). Nevertheless of the small sample size, in our study we found significantly higher levels of total protein in bee hemolymph in colonies treated with HI BEES vitamins. These results are in agreement with Shumkova and Balkanska (2021) where another product containing vitamin C (IMMUNOSTART HERB) was found to influence positively the levels of total protein in bee hemolymph. Although we did not investigate the possible link between total protein in hemolymph and brood rearing in the present study, it seems that two variables might be positively correlated which is in agreement with results of Rudelli *et al.* (2024). The significant increase of total protein in our experimental group suggests that HI BEES multivitamin composition increases protein synthesis in bee hemolymph. It should be noted, however, that there is a lack of consideration about alternative effects inherent to vitamins supplementation. Moreover, the exact mechanism of vitamin influence on protein synthesis in hemolymph is unknown and requires further investigation. For now, we can only suggest that this could be due to the influence of B-vitamin complex on vitellogenin synthesis. It is well known that B vitamins are cofactors in metabolic pathways, influencing protein synthesis and energy production. B vitamins are particularly important for amino acid metabolism and may increase protein levels in bee hemolymph (Depeint *et al.* 2006; Elsayeh *et al.* 2022). Another possible mechanism for vitamin influence on protein synthesis are antioxidant properties of vitamin C. The general effect of supplementing honey bee diet with vitamin C has been well studied (Zahra et Talal 2008; Farjan *et al.* 2012; 2014; Andi et Ahmadi 2014; Abou-Shaara *et al.* 2023) but less is known about vitamin C influence on proteins in bee hemolymph. There is a lack of data, but some studies suggest that ascorbic acid supplementation may increase hemolymph protein concentrations by reducing oxidative damage to proteins (Syama et Sreeranjit 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendation

Colonies treated with HI BEES multivitamins have increased numbers of brood and develop better. Therewithal, this study demonstrates that HI BEES multivitamin supplementation increases total protein in bee hemolymph, suggesting improved metabolic efficiency and resilience. We recommend usage of multivitamin product HI BEES during spring and autumn feeding of honeybee colonies, particularly in resource-limited environments.

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Disclosure Statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

References

1. Abou-Shaara, H., A. Amro, E. Omar. (2023). *Effects of Acetylsalicylic Acid, Echinacea Purpurea Extract, and Vitamin C on Survival, Immunity and Performance of Honey Bees*. Egypt. Acad. J. Biol. Sci., A Entomol, 16(2), 81–91.

2. Anđelković, B., G. Jevtić, M. Mladenović, M. Petrović, T. Vasić. (2011). *Influence of spring feed on the strength of honey bee colonies during spring development*. *Biotechnol. Anim. Husb.*, 27(4), 1757–1760.
3. Anderson L. M., A. Dietz. (1976). *Pyridoxine requirement of the honey bee (Apis mellifera) for brood rearing*. *Apidologie*, 7, 67–84.
4. Andi, M. A., A. Ahmadi. (2014). *Influence of vitamin C in sugar syrup on brood area, colony population, body weight and protein in honey bees*. *Int. J. Biosci.*, 4(6), 32–36.
5. Delaplane, K. S., J. Van Der Steen, E. Guzman-Novoa. (2013). *Standard methods for estimating strength parameters of Apis mellifera colonies*. *J. Apic. Res.*, 52, 1–12.
6. Depeint, F., W. R. Bruce, N. Shangari, R. Mehta, P. J. O'Brien. (2006). *Mitochondrial function and toxicity: Role of the B vitamin family on mitochondrial energy metabolism*. *Chem Biol Interact*, 163(1–2), 94–112.
7. Elsayeh, W. A., C. Cook, G. A. Wright. (2022). *B-Vitamins Influence the Consumption of Macronutrients in Honey Bees*. *Front. sustain. food syst.*, 6, 1–11.
8. Farjan, M., M. Dmitryjuk, Z. Lipiński, E. Biernat-Łopieńska, K. Żółtowska. (2012). *Supplementation of the honey bee diet with vitamin C: The effect on the antioxidative system of Apis mellifera carnica brood at different stages*. *J. Apic. Res.*, 51(3), 263–270.
9. Farjan, M., E. Łopieńska-Biernat, Z. Lipiński, M. Dmitryjuk, K. Żółtowska. (2014). *Supplementing with vitamin C the diet of honeybees (Apis mellifera carnica) parasitized with Varroa destructor: effects on antioxidative status*. *Parasitology*, 141(6), 770–776.
10. Feng, M., H. Ramadan, B. Han, Y. Fang, J. Li. (2014). *Hemolymph proteome changes during worker brood development match the biological divergences between western honey bees (Apis mellifera) and eastern honey bees (Apis cerana)*. *BMC Genomics*, 15(1), 563.
11. Fries, I., F. Feng, A. da Silva, S. B. Slemenda, N. J. Pieniazek. (1996). *Nosema ceranae n. sp. (Microspora, Nosematidae), morphological and molecular characterization of a microsporidian parasite of the Asian honey bee Apis cerana (Hymenoptera, Apidae)*. *Eur. J. Protistol.*, 32(3), 356–365.
12. Glavinic, U., B. Stankovic, V. Draskovic, J. Stevanovic, T. Petrovic, N. Lakic, Z. Stanimirovic. (2017). *Dietary amino acid and vitamin complex protects honey bee from immunosuppression caused by Nosema ceranae*. *PLoS ONE*, 12.
13. Herbert, E. W., H. Shimanuki. (1978). *Effect of fat soluble vitamins on the brood rearing capabilities of honey bees fed a synthetic diet*. *Ann. Entomol. Soc. Am.*, 71, 689–691.
14. Jovanovic, N. M., U. Glavinic, B. Delic, B. Vejnovic, N. Aleksic, V. Mladjan, Z. Stanimirovic. (2021). *Plant-based supplement containing B-complex vitamins can improve bee health and increase colony performance*. *Prev. Vet. Med.*, 190, 105322.
15. Kingsley, G. R. (1939). *The determination of serum total protein, albumin, and globulin by the Biuret reaction*. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 131(1), 197–200.
16. Rudelli, C., R. Galuppi, R. Cabbri, T. Dalmonte, L. Fontanesi, G. Andreani, G. Isani. (2024). *Field Application of an Innovative Approach to Assess Honeybee Health and Nutritional Status*. *Animals*, 14, 2183.
17. Shumkova, R., R. Balkanska. (2021). *Influence of IMMUNOSTART HERB feeding on the bee colonies development*. *Bulg. J. Agric. Sci.*, 27(5), 896–902.
18. Strachecka, A. J., K. Olszewski, J. Paleolog. (2015). *Curcumin stimulates biochemical mechanisms of Apis mellifera resistance and extends the apian life-span*. *J. Apic. Sci.*, 59(1), 129–141.

19. Syama S., V. Sreeranjit. (2022). *Evidence of diet supplementation with vitamin C protecting honeybees from Imidacloprid induced peroxidative damage: a study with Apis cerana indica*. Sociobiology, 69(3), e7763, 1–12.
20. Zahra, A., M. Talal. (2008). *Impact of pollen supplements and vitamins on the development of hypopharyngeal glands and on brood area in honey bees*. J. Apic. Sci., 52(2), 5–11.
21. Zhelyazkova, I., K. Gurgulova, I. Panchev, V. Popova. (2008). *Influence of „Startovit”, „Apitonus” and „Apaniran” on the bee colony productivity parameters*. Beekeeping – simple and clear. Book of abstracts (pp. 41–44). Bucharest, Romania, 11–14.IX. 2008.